

PIRO-2026-00108

Details

Working Title NOAA OCM Old Dominion University
Coral Nursery and Outplantings BIL grant
Request Received Jan 26, 2026

Region PIRO
Division Protected Resources Division (PRD)
Branch Intergovernmental Coordination and
Conservation Branch

Activity Details

Category	Sub-Category
Aquaculture	Coral
Construction	Installation and/or Repair of Buoys and Other Similar Structures, Survey Activities
Restoration	Coral, Marine

Primary Action Agency

US Department of Commerce (DOC) - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) National Ocean Service (NOS) - Office for Coastal Management

Species Details

Taxa	Common Name	Scientific Name	Listing Unit	Status	Designated Critical Habitat	Foreign
Coral	Coral	<i>Acropora globiceps</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✓	✗
Coral	Coral	<i>Acropora retusa</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✓	✗
Coral	Coral	<i>Acropora speciosa</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✓	✗
Coral	Coral	<i>Fimbriaphyllia paradivisa</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✓	✗
Coral	Coral	<i>Isopora crateriformis</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✗	✗
Fish	Giant Manta Ray	<i>Manta birostris</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✗	✗
Fish	Oceanic Whitetip Shark	<i>Carcharhinus longimanus</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✗	✗
Fish	Scalloped Hammerhead Shark	<i>Sphyrna lewini</i>	Indo-West Pacific DPS	Threatened Indo-West Pacific DPS	✗	✗
Mollusk	Chambered Nautilus	<i>Nautilus pompilius</i>	Range-wide	Threatened Range-wide	✗	✗
Mollusk	Smooth giant clam	<i>Tridacna derasa</i>	Range-wide	Proposed Endangered Range-wide	✗	✗
Mollusk	True giant clam	<i>Tridacna gigas</i>	Range-wide	Proposed Endangered Range-wide	✗	✗
Turtle	Green Turtle	<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	Central South Pacific DPS	Endangered Central South Pacific DPS	✗	✗

Turtle	Hawksbill Turtle	<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	Range-wide	Endangered <i>Range-wide</i>	✓	✗
Taxa	Common Name	Scientific Name	Listing Unit	Status	Designated Critical Habitat	Foreign
Turtle	Leatherback Turtle	<i>Dermochelys coriacea</i>	Range-wide	Endangered <i>Range-wide</i>	✓	✗
Turtle	Olive Ridley Turtle	<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	All Other Areas	Threatened <i>All Other Areas</i>	✗	✗
Whale	Blue Whale	<i>Balaenoptera musculus</i>	Range-wide	Endangered <i>Range-wide</i>	✗	✗
Whale	Fin Whale	<i>Balaenoptera physalus</i>	Range-wide	Endangered <i>Range-wide</i>	✗	✗
Whale	Sei Whale	<i>Balaenoptera borealis</i>	Range-wide	Endangered <i>Range-wide</i>	✗	✗
Whale	Sperm Whale	<i>Physeter macrocephalus</i>	Range-wide	Endangered <i>Range-wide</i>	✗	✗
Turtle	Loggerhead Turtle	<i>Caretta caretta</i>	South Pacific Ocean DPS	Endangered <i>South Pacific Ocean DPS</i>	✗	✓

Critical Habitat Details

Taxa	Common Name	Scientific Name	Listing Unit	Status
Turtle	Green Turtle	<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	Central South Pacific DPS	Proposed ⓘ <i>Central South Pacific DPS</i>
Coral	Fimbriaphyllia paradivisa	<i>Fimbriaphyllia paradivisa</i>	Range-wide	Designated <i>Range-wide</i>
Coral	Acropora speciosa	<i>Acropora speciosa</i>	Range-wide	Designated <i>Range-wide</i>
Coral	Acropora retusa	<i>Acropora retusa</i>	Range-wide	Designated <i>Range-wide</i>
Coral	Acropora globiceps	<i>Acropora globiceps</i>	Range-wide	Designated <i>Range-wide</i>
Coral	Isopora crateriformis	<i>Isopora crateriformis</i>	Range-wide	Designated <i>Range-wide</i>

Location Information

Country/International Waters	Foreign Waters Jurisdictional Zone	US Waters Jurisdictional Zone	State/Territory	Body of Water	HUC Level #	HUC Number
United States		State or Territory Waters	American Samoa	Other		

GIS Information

Type	Label	Lat Degrees	Lat Minutes	Lat Seconds	Lat Decimal	Long Degrees	Long Minutes	Long Seconds	Long Decimal
Point	Faga'alu	14	17	30	14.2917	170	40	43	170.6786
Point	Leone	14	20	22	14.3394	170	47	15	170.7875
Point	Nu'uuli	14	18	45	14.3125	170	41	43	170.6953